

Management of Lichen Planus through Ayurveda

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In modern science, lichen planus is treated mostly by corticosteroids but the steroids have side effects like hepatotoxicity and nephrotoxicity. Lichen planus is an immune-mediated oral and cutaneous inflammatory disease, found in 0.5% to 2.6% of general population² The prevalence of oral lichen planus in Indian population is 2.6% with more female predilection.³ The disease not only affects the patient physically but also disturbs mentally, as the appearance is very critical. In *Ayurveda*, all skin diseases are lined beneath the term *Kustha Roga*. Vitiated *Dosha* cause abnormal colour of skin and produce degenerative changes called *Kustha*⁴. *Kustha* is produced by the vitiation of seven factors i.e. three *Dosha* and four *Dushaya*.⁵ Line of treatment was chosen according to dominancy of *Dosha* involved.

Case Study

A 50 year old female presented the OPD of National Institute of Ayurveda hospital on dated 30.03.2019 complaining of papules of blackish color on whole of the body with severe itching and oral mucosa was also involved. History of present illness uncovered that the patient was normal 10 year back. All of a sudden, she suffered with severe itching on her body with white patches. Gradually, she also got black papules on the skin. Initially the papules appeared on thigh and then gradually spread on forearm and trunk region. She took allopathic treatment and got relief. After three years, again remission of disease occurred in winter season. Again she took treatment and got relief. Thus, there was a history of remission of disease after 3 or 4 years in winter season. Since, last five years she also has a history of pain in both knee joints. Personal history uncovered that the patient is a

ABSTRACT

Lichen Planus is a papulosquamous disorder that may affect the skin, scalp, nails, and mucous membranes. The primary cutaneous lesions are pruritic, polygonal, flat topped, violaceous papules. In Ayurveda, all skin diseases are lined beneath the term *Kustha Roga*. Vitiated *Dosha* cause abnormal colour of skin and produce degenerative changes called *Kustha*. CASE REPORT: A 50 year old female came to OPD of National Institute of Ayurveda, Jaipur having complains of black papules on her whole body for last 10 years. Oral mucosa was also involved. *Mahamanjishtha Kwatha*, *Trivrit Leha*, *Tikta Ghrita*, *Khadiradi Vati* and a combination of *Rasamanikaya*, *Shuddha Gandhaka*, *Manjishthadi Churna*, was given orally, *Eladi Taila* was given for local application and *Irimedadi Taila* was given for *Gandusha*. RESULTS: Patient got significant relief in itching and discolouration of skin. Ayurvedic principle of *Kustha* is effective in the management of Lichen Planus.

KEYWORDS: *Dosha, Dushaya, Kustha, Lichen planus*

INTRODUCTION

Lichen Planus is a papulosquamous disorder that may affect the skin, scalp, nails, and mucous membranes. The primary cutaneous lesions are pruritic, polygonal, flat topped, violaceous papules. Purple polygonal papules marked by severe pruritus; lacy white markings, especially associated with mucous membrane lesions. The skin lesions may occur anywhere but have a predilection for the wrists, shins, lower back, and genitalia.¹

vegetarian with reduced appetite, disturbed sleep and having frequency of micturition 5-6 times per day and having history of constipation. There was no any relevant family history of skin diseases.

Diagnostic Focus and assessment:

Laboratory investigations were as follows (Hemoglobin (12.8%), ESR (8mm/hr) and serum uric acid (3.9mg/dl) were in normal range and RA Factor was negative (8.40 IU/ml), CRP was (2.19mg/dl) was also under reference range. On 04/05/2019, histopathology examination was advised and it discovered epidermis with mild hyperkeratosis, oedema and collagen deposition. Dermis showed perivascular infiltration by nonspecific inflammatory cells. (Figure 1)

Therapeutic Intervention:

Mahamanjishtha Kwatha, a combination of *Rasamanikaya*, *Shuddha Gandhaka*, *Manjishthadi Churna*, *Khadiradi Vati* was given orally, *Eladi Taila* was given for local application and *Irimedadi Taila* was given for *Gandusha* (Table No.1). Initially, this treatment was given for seven days to see initial response; on seventh day patient got 25% relief in itching. So, this treatment was continued.

Follow up and Outcomes:-

The patient was on follow up on every fifteen days till two months. Gradually papules and plaques started disappearing and there was relief in itching during follow up. After two month of treatment, patient got complete relief from itching and new papules do not formed on the body. Old papules

were slightly reduced and colour of papules also become faint. There is no reoccurrence of disease even after four months. (Table No.2)

Discussion

Diagnosis in this case was made on the basis of classical black to purple papules on thigh, forearm, wrists, ankle and oral mucosa accompanied with severe itching. In *Ayurveda*, all skin diseases are lined beneath the term *Kustha Roga*. Vitiated *Dosha* cause abnormal colour of skin and produce degenerative changes called *Kustha*. *Kustha* is produced by the vitiation of seven factors i.e. three *Dosha* and four *Dushaya*. Due to *Ahitakara Nidana Sevana*, first these three *Dosha Vata, Pitta* and *Kapha* get vitiated and that they additionally vitiate *Twak, Rakta, Lasika* and *Mamsa*. *Aacharya Charaka* while describing *Kustha* treatment very firstly has mentioned that all *Kustha* are *Tridoshaja* in nature and should be treated according to dominancy of *Dosha*. First treat the dominant *Dosha* then rest of the vitiated *Dosha* should be treated⁶. Patient was treated on the principle of management of *Kushtha Roga*. In the present case patient had symptoms of mainly vitiated *Kapha Dosha* i.e. severe itching, hyperkeratosis on whole of the body associated with symptoms of Vitiated *Vata Dosha (Karshnyata)*. So, we advised drug according to dominancy of *Dosha* involved. some of these drug were *Kusthahara (Rasamanikaya, Manjishthaadi Kshaya, Panchtikta Ghrita, eladi Taila), Raktaprasadak(Manjishthadi Churna), Kaphashamaka (Rasamanikaya, Manjishthaadi Kshaya, Eladi Taila), Vatashamaka(Rasamanikaya, Panchtikta Ghrita, Eladi Taila), Trivrit leha is Mridu Virechaka*, it is used for *Nitya Shodhana* and because oral mucosa was also involve; so, *Khadiradi Vati* and *Irimeadi Taila* was also advised for *Gandusha* (Gargles) because both of these drug are drug of choice of treatment in *Mukha Roga* (Table No.3). By this treatment, vitiated *Dosha* comes in balance state and symptoms of vitiated *Dosha* subside gradually. And patient got significant relief.

Conclusion

Lichen Planus is an autoimmune disease involving skin and oral mucosa; it is notorious for its reoccurrence. Treatment options of conventional system of medicine in lichen planus have very side effects. Line of treatment of *Kustha* is safe and effective in Lichen Planus symptomatically.

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Table No. 1 showing days and dosage of Shaman treatment

Name of the Drug used	Dose	Route of administration
Rasamanikaya+Shuddha Gandhaka+Manjishthadi Churna	125mg+250mg+5gm twice a day	Oral
Panchtikta Ghrita	10 ml twice a day	Oral
Manjishthadi Kasaya	20 ml twice a day	Oral
Khadiradi Vati	6 tablet in a day	Oral
Trivrit Leha	5gm twice a day	Oral
Eladi Taila	-	Local application
Irimeadi Taila	10 ml	Oral (Gandushartha)

Table No.2: Improvement in complaints of Lichen planus patient after Shaman chikitsa

Symptoms	Before treatment	After one month of treatment	After two month of treatment
Papule size	2-3 mm	Same	Slightly reduced
Colour	Dark black	Slightly faint	Slightly faint
Itching	+++++	+++	+
New papule formation	2-3 per week	Nil	Nil

Table No.3 showing ingredients, properties and action of the drugs given.

Drug	Ingredients	Properties and action
Rasamanikaya ⁷	Hartala(Arsenic Sulphde)	VataKaphashamaka, useful in skin disease like Kustha, Visharpa, Vipadika, Vicharchika
Panchatikta Ghrita ⁸	Neem(Azadirachta indica), Patola(Trichosanthes dioica), Kateri(Solanum indicum),Vasa(Adhatoda vasica), Giloya(Tinospora cordifolia), Amalaki(Emblica officinalis), Haritaki(Terminalia chebula) and Baheda(Terminalia bellirica),Goghrita(cow ghee)	Ushna, Tikshna, Vyavayi, Vikasi, Katu , Tikta Rasa and Katu Vipaka, useful in Kustha, Vattapittakapha Vikara, Dustha Rakta Vikara.
Manjishthadi Churna ⁹	Manjishtha(Rubia Cordifolia), Choti elaichi(Elettaria cardamomum), Saunf(Foeniculum Vulgare), Saunageru(Red Ochre), Pashanbheda(Bergenian Ligulata), Sanaya(Cassia Angustifolia)	Raktashodhaka,Pittashamaka
Manjishthadi Kasaya ¹⁰	Manjishta(Rubia cordifolia),Musta (Cyperus rotundus),Kutaja(Holarrhena antidysenterica), Guduchi(Tinospora cordifolia), Kushta(Saussurea lappa),Nagara (ginger), Bharngi(Clerodendron serratum), Kshudra(Solanum xanthocarpum), Vacha(Acorus calamus), Nimba (Azadirachta indica) ,Haridra(Turmeric), Daruharidra(Berberisaristata), Haritaki(Terminalia chebula), Vibhitaki (Terminalia bellirica),Amla (Emblica officinalis), Patola (Luffa acutangula) ,Katuka(Picrorrhiza kurroa), Murva (Marsdenia tenacissima),Vidanga(Embelia ribes),Asana(Pterocarpus marsupium), Chitraka (Plumbago zeylanica), Shatavari (Asparagus racemosus),Trayamana(Gentiana kurroo) Krishna(Long pepper),Indrayava (Holarrhena antidysenterica),Vasa(Adhatoda vasica)Bhringaraja (Eclipta alba), Mahadaru (Cedrus deodara), Patha(Cissampelos pariera), Khadira(Acacia catechu),Chandana(Santalum album),Trivrit(Operculina turpethum),Varuna(Crataeva nurvala), Kiratatikta (Swertia chirata), Bakuchi (Psoralea corylifolia), Kritamala (Cassia fistula),Shakhotaka(Streblus asper), Mahanimba(Melia azadirachata), Karanja(Pongamia pinnata), Ativisha(Aconitum heterophyllum), Jala(Pavonia odorata), Indravaruni (Citrullus cholestyis),Ananta(Hemidesmus indicus),Sariva (Hemidesmus indicus),Parpata (Fumaria indica)	KaphapittaVikara and Kusthahara
Khadiradi Vati ¹¹	Khadira (Acacia catechu),Arimeda(Acacia leucophloea /farnesiana),Chandana(Santalum album),Padmaka (Prunus puddum/ cerasoides), Usheera(Vetiveria zizanioides),Manjishta (Rubia cordifolia), Dhataki (Woodfordia fruticosa),Ghana (Cyperus rotundus),Prapaundarika(Nymphaea stellata),Yashti (Glycyrrhizaglabra), Twak (Cinnamomum zeylanicum), Ela(Elettaria cardamomum), Padma (Nelumbium speciosum), Nagakeshara (Mesua ferrea), Laksha(Laccifer lacca),Rasanjana – Aqueous extract of Berberis aristata, Mamsi(Nardostachys jatamansi),Haritaki (Terminalia chebula),Vibhitaki (Terminalia bellirica),Amalaki (Emblica officinalis / Phyllanthus emblica),Lodhra (Symplocos racemosa), Balaka(Pavonia odorata),Haridra (Curcuma Longa),Daruharidra (Berberis aristata),Phalini (Callicarpa macrophylla),Ela(Elettaria cardamomum),Samanga Rubia cordifolia), katphala(Myrica nagi), Vacha(Acorus calamus), Yavasa(Fagonia cretica/Arabica), Agarar(Aquilaria agallocha), Pattanga(Caesalpinia sappan), Gairika(Purified red ochre),Anjana – Aqueous extract of Berberis aristata),Lavanga (Syzigium aromaticum),Nakha (Capparis zeylanica), Kankola(Piper cubeba),Jatikosha (Myristica fragrans), Karpooa (Cinnamomum camphora)	Effective in Mukha Roga
Trivrit Leha ¹²	Trivrit (Operculina turpethum)	Virechaka

<p>Irimedadi Taila¹³</p>	<p>Yashti (Glycyrrhiza glabra),Trijatha (Cinnamon, cardamom and Cinnamomum tamala),Manjishta (Rubia cordifolia), Gayatri (Acacia catechu),Lodhra (Symplocos racemosa),Katphala (Myrica nagi), Irimeda Twak (Acacia leucophloea /farnesiana), Musta (Cyperus rotundus),Agaru (Aquilaria agallocha),Shveta Chandana (Santalum album),Rakta Chandana (Pterocarpus santalinus),Karpooora (Cinnamomum camphora), Jati (Myristica fragrans),Takkola (Illicium verum),Mamsi (Nardostachys jatamansi),Dhataki (Woodfordia fruticosa),Gairika (Red ochre),Mrinala (Cymbopogon jwarancusa),Mishi (Anethum sowa), Vaidehi (Piper longum), Padmakesara(Nelumbo nucifera), Kumkuma (Crocus sativus), Laksha (Laccifer lacca), Manjishta(Rubia cordifolia),Brihati (Solanum indicum), Bilvapatra(Aegle marmelos), Suradruma – Cedrus deodara), Shaileya (Asphaltum), Sarala(Pinus roxburghi), Sprikka (Frlphinium zalil), Palasha – Butea monosperma),Rajani(Curcuma longa), Daruhaaridra (Berberis aristata), Priyangu (Callicarpa macrophylla), Tejani (Clematis triloba), Pradhakaleya (Cosciniun fenestratum), Pushkara (Inula raceomsa), Jaya(butilon theophrasti), Vyaghri(Solanum xanthocarpum), Madana(Randia dumetorum), Tila Taila- Sesame oil(Sesamum indicum), Arimeda(Acacia leucophloea), Nyagrodha(Ficus bengalensis), Udumbara (Ficus racemosa), Ashwattha (Ficus religiosa), Plaksha(Ficus lacor</p>	<p>Effective in all Mukha Roga</p>
<p>Eladi Taila¹⁴</p>	<p>Tila taila (Oil of Sesamum indicum), Ela (Elettaria cardamomum),Sthoola Ela (Amomum subulatum), Turushka (Hydnocarpus laurifolia), Kushta (Saussurea lappa), Phalini(Callicarpa macrophylla), Mamsi (Nardostachys jatamansi), Jaladhyamaka (Coleus zeylanicus) ,Sprikka(Anisomeles malabarica), Choraka (Angelica archagelica), Chochapatra (Cinnamomum zeylanicum), Tagara(Valeriana wallichii), Sthauneya – Taxus baccata, Jati(Myristica fragrans) , Rasa(Commiphora myrrha), Shukti(Ostrea edulis), Vyaghranakha (Capparis sepiaria), Marahva (Cedrus deodara), Aguru (Aquilaria agallocha), Shrivasaka (Pinus longifolia), Kumkuma (Crocus sativus),Chanda (Costus speciosus),Guggulu (Commiphora mukul),Devadhupa (Shorea robusta),Khapura (Boswellia serrata),Punnaga (Calophyllum inophyllum),Nagahva – Mesua ferrea</p>	<p>VataKaphashamaka, Varnaprasadana, Kandu,Pitika,Kothanashak</p>

Before treatment:-

After treatment:-

